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Trends in Antidepressants Use in Spain between 2015 and 2018: Analyses from a Population-Based Registry Study with Reference to Driving

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Abstract: Antidepressants are considered driving-impairing medicines (DIM). This is a population-based registry study that shows the trend in the use of antidepressants in Castile and León, Spain, from 2015 to 2018. Data on antidepressant dispensations at pharmacies and the adjusted use of these medicines by the driver population are presented. For the purposes of analysis, population distribution by age and gender has been taken into account, as well as the three Driving Under the Influence of Drugs, alcohol, and medicines (DRUID) categories. Antidepressants were used by 8.56% of the general population and 5.66% of drivers. Antidepressants were used more commonly by females than by males (12.12% vs. 4.87%, $\chi^2 = 1325.124$, $p = 0.001$), and users increased as the age increased, even if women who drive used less antidepressants after turning 60 years of age. Chronic use of antidepressants was relevant (8.28%) in the same way as daily use (3.15%). Most of the consumption included SSRIs (4.99%), which are also known as “other antidepressants” (3.71%). Regardless of antidepressants consumed, users took 2.75 ± 1.19 DIMs, which are mainly anxiolytics (58.80%) and opioids (26.43%). Lastly, regarding consumption of antidepressants according to the DRUID classification, category I predominated over categories II and III. Our findings should serve as a starting point for health and traffic authorities to raise awareness of the risk for traffic accidents, especially involving SSRIs.

Keywords: antidepressants; driving impairing medicines; automobile driving; drug utilization; traffic accidents

1. Introduction

Depression causes severe disabilities in the occupational and social life of patients [1] and it is currently recognized as a global public health concern [2]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), major depressive disorder will become the second leading cause of disability around the world in 2030 [2]. Depression affects nearly 10% of the adult population, and has a lifetime prevalence of approximately 13% [3]. In addition, depression is the ninth most frequent chronic disease among people over 14 years of age, which is more frequent in women than in men [4].

Depression is characterized by loss of energy and cognitive impairment of the patient [5], and it is associated with lethargy and sleep disturbances, which affect daily functions [6], including the fitness to drive [7]. Mobility is fundamental for the independence of the individual in society today [8], and different studies indicate that 80% of patients with depression have a valid driver's license and 70% drive regularly [9]. Although the objective of pharmacological treatment with antidepressants is long-term remission of symptoms and improved daily activity of patients [8], antidepressants can affect the safety of driving [9,10].

Antidepressants that hold the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) code N06 are classified in four subgroups [11]: (1) non-selective monoamine reuptake inhibitors (or tricyclic antidepressants, TCAs) (N06A), (2) selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) (N06B), (3) non-selective monoamine oxidase A inhibitors (N06AF), (4) monoamine oxidase A inhibitors (N06AG), and (5) "other antidepressants" (N06AX). Each of these antidepressant types has a particular side-effects profile. For instance, TCAs can cause sedation, dizziness, double and blurred vision, tachycardia, and a tremor [12]. SSRIs are associated with nausea, diarrhea, insomnia, nervousness, agitation, and anxiety [13]. Sedation and the impairment of driver's abilities are important with TCAs (e.g., amitriptyline, nortriptyline) and the noradrenergic and specific serotonergic antidepressants (NaSSAs) (e.g., mianserine, mirtazapine) belonging to the N06AX subgroup. On the contrary, SSRIs (e.g., as paroxetine, fluoxetine, escitalopram), the other serotonin receptor antagonist and reuptake inhibitors (SARIs) (e.g., trazodone), and the serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs) (e.g., venlafaxine, duloxetine) are well tolerated considering their lower sedative effect.

Currently, SSRIs have practically replaced TCAs due to their greater tolerability and safety [13]. Studies report on Odds Ratios (OR) from 1.10 to 3.10 for the risk of a traffic accident when being under antidepressant treatment [14], which highlights the risk of increasing doses of TCAs [15–18] as a clear relation involving exclusively the use of TCAs that is not confirmed [19]. On the other hand, among studies that assessed the influence of non-sedative antidepressants, such as SSRIs and venlafaxine, a slight or no increase in the risk of traffic accidents was found [18,19].

Importantly, antidepressants are present in the three Driving Under the Influence of Drugs, alcohol and medicines (DRUID) categories: SSRIs and monoamine oxidase A inhibitors belong to category I (minor influence on fitness to drive), TCAs belong to categories II (moderate influence on fitness to drive), and III (severe influence on fitness to drive), and the so-called "other antidepressants" (ATC subgroup N06AX) may be encountered into category III (e.g., mianserin, trazodone), or categories I and II (e.g., venlafaxine, duloxetine) (Table S1) [20].

Trends in antidepressants use by the population is a topic of great interest. Since commercialization of SSRIs, an increase in their use for two to three times may be observed in western countries [21,22]. For instance, in Spain, the use of antidepressants increased by 200% between 2000 and 2013, and, in a similar way as in European Union (EU) countries, SSRIs were the most consumed (70.4%) [23]. However, there is still little information regarding the use of SSRIs and driving risks. In Spain, a specific pictogram on "medicines and driving" was introduced in 2011 on the packaging of all driving-impairing medicines (DIM), including all antidepressants. The main objective of this pictogram was to improve patient and physician knowledge about the effects of these medicines on the ability to drive safely [24].

This study presents the data on antidepressants consumption from 2015 to 2018 in Castile and León, Spain, based on dispensation of such DIMs at pharmacies. The adjusted use of antidepressants by the driver population is also presented in order to assess differences in patterns of use with respect to the general population [24–27]. In addition, the duration and their concomitant use of antidepressants with other driving impairing medicines were also assessed. Distributions by age and gender, and the use of antidepressants into the three DRUID categories were considered [20].

2. Experimental Section

This manuscript presents findings from a population-based registry study carried out according to the Reporting of studies Conducted using Observational Routinely-collected Data (RECORD)

recommendations in order to adequately provide real-world evidence into the topic addressed [28]. Our findings cover dispensation of all commercialized antidepressants in Castile and León, Spain (ATC subgroups N06AA, N06AB, N06AG, and N06AX) from 2015 to 2018.

For a better understanding of our results, separately, antidepressants into each of DRUID categories were studied (Table S1). The data on dispensation of antidepressants and other DIMs were accessible from CONCYLIA (<http://www.saludcastillayleon.es/portalmedicamento/es/indicadores-informes/concylia>), where the entire information on pharmaceuticals care in Castile and León is routinely collected. The drivers' license census data for the years 2015 to 2018 were also accessible (<http://www.dgt.es/es/seguridad-vial/estadisticas-e-indicadores/permisos-conduccion/>) to calculate the adjusted use of antidepressants by drivers (Table S2), as previously made [24–27].

For the purposes of an analysis in a real-world setting, all dispensations were considered as equivalent to consumption. Although consumption of antidepressants in hospitals and private clinics was not considered, our findings cover more than 95% of uses since the entire Spanish population is included in the public health system and antidepressants are mandatory prescription drugs.

The following variables were considered: (1) yearly frequency of antidepressants consumption, (2) acute (1–7 days), sub-acute (8–29 days), and chronic use (≥ 30 days) of antidepressants each year, (3) yearly frequency of daily use of antidepressants, (4) yearly frequency of antidepressants consumption by DRUID categories, and (5) concomitant use of antidepressants with other DIMs during each year. All analyses were done considering age and gender distributions. This study was approved by our local ethics committee on 17 March 2016 (reference number PI 16-387).

Results are expressed as frequencies (percentage) with their corresponding 95% confidence interval (95% CI) or as means accompanied by their standard deviations (SD). Differences between continuous variables were calculated using Student's t-test, and those between categorical variables were calculated using Pearson's chi-squared test. The Cochran-Armitage trend test was used to evaluate the consumption trend by years. The level of significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed by using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 24.0., SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL). Lastly, Microsoft Word and Excel (Microsoft Office version 365, Microsoft, Redmon, WA, USA) were used for preparing this manuscript.

3. Results

From 2015 to 2018, 8.56% of the general population took at least one antidepressant. Their use was three times greater in women than in men (12.12% vs. 4.87%, $\chi^2 = 1325.124$, $p = 0.001$, Table 1), and, in both sexes, the consumption increased as the age increased (Figure 1), which involved the four ATC subgroups (Figure 2). Overall, yearly antidepressant consumption increased 21.18% ($Z = 57.216$, $p < 0.0001$) from 2015 (7.64%) to 2018 (9.26%), and this increase involved particularly chronic use (21.80%, $Z = 57.607$, $p < 0.0001$) (7.38% in 2015 vs. 8.98 in 2018) and daily use (25.80%, $Z = 43.183$, $p < 0.0001$) (2.76% in 2015 vs 3.48 in 2018). Regarding the increase in the study period, no differences were observed between men and women (Figure 3). Chronic use (≥ 30 days) was the most frequent (97.73%), but 3.15% of the population took at least one antidepressant daily (Table 1). In addition, concomitant use of antidepressants with other DIMs was common. Regardless of antidepressants consumed (Table 2), yearly users took 2.75 ± 1.19 DIMs (anxiolytics, 58.80%, opioids, 26.43%) and daily users took 2.91 ± 1.21 DIMs (anxiolytics, 67.18%, opioids, 28.89%).

Table 1. Antidepressants consumption according to the CONCYLIA database and the Castile and León drivers' license census data.

Type of Antidepressant	Population Using Antidepressants % (95CI)					Drivers Using Antidepressants % (95CI)				
	Yearly Use	Daily Use	Type of Use			Yearly Use	Daily Use	Type of Use		
			Acute	Subacute	Chronic			Acute	Subacute	Chronic
<i>Total Antidepressants</i>										
TOTAL	8.56 (8.52–8.59)	3.15 (3.13–3.17)	0.05 (0.04–0.06)	0.23 (0.22–0.24)	8.28 (8.25–8.32)	5.66 (5.62–5.70)	1.93 (1.91–1.95)	0.04 (0.03–0.05)	0.21 (0.20–0.21)	5.41 (5.37–5.44)
Male	4.87 (4.83–4.91)	1.68 (1.65–1.70)	0.03 (0.02–0.04)	0.15 (0.14–0.15)	4.70 (4.66–4.74)	4.83 (4.78–4.87)	1.68 (1.65–1.70)	0.03 (0.02–0.04)	0.16 (0.15–0.16)	4.64 (4.60–4.69)
Female	12.12 (12.06–12.17)	4.57 (4.54–4.61)	0.07 (0.06–0.08)	0.31 (0.30–0.32)	11.74 (11.68–11.80)	6.90 (6.83–6.96)	2.31 (2.27–2.35)	0.07 (0.06–0.08)	0.16 (0.15–0.17)	4.64 (4.59–4.70)
	$\chi^2 = 1325.124$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 4531.330$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 32.612$; p = 0.013	$\chi^2 = 76.08$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 7024.208$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 14360.161$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 14615.499$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 1160.409$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 6083.759$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 43897.32$; p = 0.001
<i>Non-selective monoamine reuptake inhibitors</i>										
TOTAL	1.11 (1.10–1.13)	0.05 (0.04–0.05)	0.17 (0.16–0.17)	0.30 (0.29–0.31)	0.64 (0.63–0.65)	0.80 (0.70–0.90)	0.04 (0.03–0.05)	0.14 (0.13–0.15)	0.24 (0.24–0.25)	0.42 (0.41–0.43)
Male	0.58 (0.57–0.59)	0.03 (0.03–0.04)	0.08 (0.08–0.09)	0.16 (0.15–0.17)	0.34 (0.32–0.35)	0.61 (0.59–0.63)	0.04 (0.03–0.05)	0.09 (0.08–0.10)	0.17 (0.16–0.18)	0.35 (0.34–0.36)
Female	1.63 (1.61–1.65)	0.06 (0.05–0.06)	0.25 (0.24–0.26)	0.44 (0.43–0.45)	0.94 (0.92–0.96)	1.10 (0.99–1.12)	0.03 (0.02–0.04)	0.21 (0.2–0.22)	0.35 (0.34–0.37)	0.53 (0.51–0.55)
	$\chi^2 = 48.521$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 306.885$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 36.373$; p = 0.004	$\chi^2 = 51.54$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 392.684$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 1837.676$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 113.888$; p = 0.023	$\chi^2 = 1149.338$; p = 0.013	$\chi^2 = 2029.683$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 3326.979$; p = 0.001
<i>Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors</i>										
TOTAL	4.99 (4.96–5.02)	2.22 (2.20–2.24)	-	0.23 (0.22–0.24)	4.76 (4.73–4.79)	3.32 (3.29–3.35)	1.33 (1.31–1.35)	-	0.19 (0.18–0.20)	3.13 (3.10–3.16)
Male	2.69 (2.66–2.72)	1.16 (1.14–1.18)	-	0.30 (0.29–0.31)	0.64 (0.63–0.66)	2.69 (2.65–2.72)	1.14 (1.12–1.16)	-	0.14 (0.13–0.15)	2.55 (2.51–2.58)
Female	7.22 (7.17–7.26)	3.24 (3.21–3.27)	-	0.32 (0.31–0.33)	6.90 (6.85–6.94)	4.26 (4.21–4.32)	1.62 (1.59–1.65)	-	0.26 (0.25–0.27)	4.00 (3.95–4.05)
	$\chi^2 = 1009.602$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 2947.450$; p = 0.001	-	$\chi^2 = 114.15$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 4329.346$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 6700.641$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 10488.675$; p = 0.001	-	$\chi^2 = 1231.407$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 23530.089$; p = 0.001
<i>Other antidepressants</i>										
TOTAL	3.71 (3.69–3.74)	0.97 (0.96–0.99)	-	0.43 (0.42–0.44)	3.28 (3.26–3.3)	2.36 (2.34–2.39)	0.62 (0.61–0.63)	-	0.31 (0.30–0.32)	2.05 (2.03–2.07)
Male	2.31 (2.28–2.34)	0.54 (0.53–0.55)	-	0.29 (0.28–0.30)	2.02 (1.99–2.04)	2.24 (2.21–2.27)	0.56 (0.54–0.57)	-	0.29 (0.28–0.30)	1.95 (1.93–1.98)
Female	5.07 (5.03–5.11)	1.39 (1.37–1.41)	-	0.56 (0.55–0.57)	4.51 (4.47–4.54)	2.54 (2.50–2.58)	0.71 (0.69–0.73)	-	0.35 (0.33–0.36)	2.19 (2.15–2.23)
	$\chi^2 = 661.836$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 1423.581$; p = 0.001	-	$\chi^2 = 98.22$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 3157.1$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 5506.160$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 4202.911$; p = 0.001	-	$\chi^2 = 2613.557$; p = 0.001	$\chi^2 = 16278.972$; p = 0.001

Abbreviations: 95CI. confidence interval.

Figure 1. Frequency of antidepressants use by the general population and the driver population.

Figure 2. Frequency of use by the type of antidepressant.

Surprisingly, among the 40 DIMs with the highest number of packages dispensed in Castile and León during the covered period, 11 were antidepressants, especially escitalopram, sertraline, mirtazapine, and venlafaxine (Table S3). SSRIs were the most consumed type of antidepressants (4.99%) regardless of gender, which is followed by the “other antidepressants” (ATC subgroup N06AX) (3.71%) and TCAs (1.11%) (Table 1). The increase in the use of new N06AX antidepressants should also be highlighted (Table S4): desvenlafaxine (56.90%), mirtazapine (34.68%), and sertraline (32.44%). Among daily users, 7 out of 10 were taking SSRIs. TCAs appeared only related to acute use (<7 days) that was infrequent (0.05%). The use of monoamine oxidase A inhibitors (N06AG) was negligible (18 patients into the covered period, $8.78 \times 10^{-6}\%$).

Consumption of antidepressants in the DRUID category I was twice compared to those in category II and 1.5 times higher than those in category III. Nevertheless, the highest increase in the use corresponded to antidepressants in category III (40.84%), which is followed by those in categories II (18.84%) and I (13.44%) (Figure 4 and Table S5).

Figure 3. Evolution of antidepressants use in Castile and León (2015–2018).

Table 2. Other driving-impairing medicines (DIMs) used concomitantly with antidepressants.

ATC Code	Description	Population % (95CI)				Drivers % (95CI)			
		Yearly Use		Daily Use		Yearly Use		Daily Use	
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
N05B	Ansyolitics	53.65 (53.36–53.94)	60.80 (60.51–61.09)	61.21 (60.52–61.89)	69.3 (68.91–69.68)	55.22 (54.75–55.7)	61.89 (61.42–62.37)	62.75 (61.97–63.53)	71.85 (71.09–72.60)
		$\chi^2 = 1026.420; p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 845.748; p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 6479.230; p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 2593.569; p = 0.001$	
N02A	Opioids	20.84 (20.5–21.17)	28.61 (28.38–28.84)	20.77 (20.20–21.34)	31.76 (31.37–32.15)	20.53 (20.14–20.91)	23.33 (22.92–23.74)	20.43 (19.78–21.08)	26.49 (25.75–27.23)
		$\chi^2 = 399.964, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 378.297, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 3344.400, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 1178.273, p = 0.001$	
N02B	Other analgesics and antipiretics	16.15 (15.84–16.45)	20.59 (20.39–20.8)	15.96 (15.45–16.47)	22.53 (22.18–22.88)	15.40 (15.06–15.74)	16 (15.64–16.35)	15.08 (14.50–15.66)	17.67 (17.03–18.31)
		$\chi^2 = 229.200, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 201.621, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 2612.735, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 939.163, p = 0.001$	
N05C	Hypnotics and Sedatives	17.33 (17.01–17.64)	17.16 (16.97–17.36)	18.63 (18.08–19.18)	19.81 (19.48–20.14)	16.97 (16.61–17.33)	14.64 (14.30–14.98)	18.56 (17.93–19.19)	18.85 (18.19–19.50)
		$\chi^2 = 235.223, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 188.963, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 2087.480, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 835.451, p = 0.001$	
N03A	Antiepileptics	19.14 (18.82–19.47)	16.28 (16.09–16.47)	24.48 (23.88–25.08)	20.93 (20.59–21.27)	20.24 (19.86–20.62)	17.67 (17.30–18.04)	26.30 (25.59–27.01)	25.58 (24.84–26.31)
		$\chi^2 = 362.380, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 359.500, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 1878.187, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 775.130, p = 0.001$	
N05A	Antipsychotics	20.73 (20.40–21.06)	15.43 (15.25–15.62)	29.39 (28.75–30.03)	20.20 (19.86–20.53)	20.71 (20.32–21.09)	13.44 (13.11–13.77)	30.76 (30.02–31.51)	20.96 (20.27–21.64)
		$\chi^2 = 1082.860, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 876.871, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 1435.496, p = 0.001$		$\chi^2 = 610.888, p = 0.001$	
Average of Driving Impairing Medicines. Population Antidepressants Use		2.74 ± 1.14	2.76 ± 1.18	2.86 ± 1.12	2.92 ± 1.23	2.73 ± 1.31	2.59 ± 1.37	2.89 ± 1.35	2.88 ± 1.43
		t = -2.951; p = 0.003		t = -7.255; p = 0.001		t = 20.608; p = 0.001		t = 1.150; p = 0.250	

Abbreviations: 95CI. confidence interval.

Figure 4. Frequency of use by Driving Under the Influence of Drugs, alcohol, and medicines (DRUID) classification.

The results obtained for drivers were similar: 5.66% used antidepressants and 1.93% took these medicines every day (Table 1). As for the general population, chronic use was the most frequent. The use of antidepressants increased with age, and, in the case of women, a peak was reached in

the age range group of 55–59 years, which is 20 years earlier than in men (Figure 1). There were no differences in concomitant DIM use between daily and non-daily users (Table 2).

4. Discussion

Our results show that the increase in antidepressants consumption between 2015 and 2018 in Castile and León, Spain was relevant. In each year of the study period, women users predominated over men users in both the general population and the driver population. With respect to the type of antidepressant, SSRIs were the most commonly used. In addition, antidepressants were mostly consumed chronically, and acute and subacute use was practically insignificant. More than half of individuals who used antidepressants during the study period also used other DIMs concomitantly, which can seriously influence fitness to drive.

The increase in the prevalence of antidepressant use is consistent with other national data and comparable with those obtained in other European countries: SSRIs and the “other antidepressants” (ATC subgroup N06AX) were the most consumed [21–23]. It is important to differentiate between classic N06AX antidepressants, such as mianserin or trazodone, that are less used, and the most recent ones, such as venlafaxine, mirtazapine, etc., which are trendy.

Antidepressants are the second most prescribed psychotropic medication for the elderly, with the first being benzodiazepines [29]. According to our results, consumption in patients in the age range group of 70–74 years was significantly higher than in younger individuals, and this fact is consistent with the results emanating from other studies that present a prevalence of 11% in North America [30] and 12% in Europe (France) [31]. Older women used the most common antidepressants. Likely, high predisposition for depressive disorders among older women may explain the use of antidepressants observed [32].

Notwithstanding, the increase in antidepressants consumption may be due to other factors different from the prevalence of depression itself. An increase in detection by physicians, and an increase in clinical indications for antidepressants, e.g., neuropathic pain (TCAs) or for smoking cessation (bupropion) [23], should be taken into account. New clinical indications have appeared because different effects on cognitive function require antidepressants at doses substantially lower than those for depression [29]. A relevant percentage of antidepressant prescriptions, i.e., amitriptyline and duloxetine, may be due to chronic pain (prevalence of 62% in people over 75 years of age) [21].

Antidepressants are mainly used chronically (≥ 30 days). A total of 40% of antidepressants were prescribed for more than 180 days, which is, according to the average use of these medications, 251 to 525 days for SSRIs that are frequently switched to SNRIs [21]. Furthermore, antidepressants are not used as monotherapy. Particularly in the elderly, the concomitant use of benzodiazepines to treat anxiety is frequent. Traffic accidents increase when using both antidepressants and benzodiazepines including 37% in the case of SSRIs and 54% in the case of TCAs [33].

The effect on fitness to drive is not only due to medication. The depressive disorder also influences this factor [34]. Depression is associated with slower reaction time in the driving simulator [35], and patients with these disorders have deficits in cognitive abilities that can cause driving errors and intensify aggressive responses to frustrating roadway events [34]. Additionally, depression is often associated with suicidal ideation, which may increase the risk of an unintended and self-harm traffic accident [3].

Remarkably, the evidence on how antidepressants affect fitness to drive is contradictory, and there are studies that did not support a direct relation [36]. For example, in the case of mirtazapine, there are studies that indicate an important driving impairment on the first day of administration, which decreases thereafter [37]. Similar observations may be found in the case of TCAs, where gradual tolerance may be affirmed [38]. Particularly, experimental studies highlight the significance of the deterioration of driving abilities when compared to healthy controls [5], but these findings are pending to confirm in large real-world prospective assessments [3]. Furthermore, controversies when classifying SSRIs by different existing classifications should be considered. The French Agency for

Health Products Safety considers these antidepressants into level 2, i.e., these medicines could affect the ability to drive and require medical advice from a physician or a pharmacist before use. According to the International Council on Alcohol, Drugs, and Traffic Safety (ICADTS), SSRIs belong to category I, i.e., these medicines are presumed to be well tolerated or unlikely to produce an effect on driving abilities [10]. Lastly, according to the DRUID classification, SSRIs are included in category I, which has a minor influence on fitness to drive [20]. In general terms, SSRIs are being considered to have a lower impact on fitness to drive, even though $OR > 2$ may be found [39,40].

On the other hand, the conclusions obtained by Ravera et al. [10] and Brunnauer et al. [8,14] when analyzing different experimental studies indicate that SSRIs do not present a high risk for driving vehicles, unless treatment is at high doses or there is concomitant consumption with other DIMs.

It is considered important to remember that the psychomotor impairment of the patient with depression may have a greater impact on the increased risk of a traffic crash than the antidepressant treatment itself [34,35]. Furthermore, by improving clinical symptoms, including drowsiness, antidepressants can increase driving safety in these patients [35].

Regardless of the need for more research, health professionals should be aware of the possible risks and have to inform their patients individually on adverse effects of antidepressants and concomitant use with other medications [10].

Lastly, this study has some limitations. First, antidepressants dispensation cannot be considered as an equivalent to antidepressants consumption, as beneficiaries of our health system could have not consumed such medicines. Second, consumption in hospitals and by private prescriptions were not taken into account. However, in this case, it can be assumed that the biases produced when using dispensing data is not relevant, as antidepressants are financed medicines and their use require mandatory medical prescription. On the other hand, CONCYLIA does not include driver's license information, so weighting was made on the basis of age and gender with the driver's license census information, as performed in previous studies by our team [24–27].

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, the use of antidepressants was frequent especially with chronic and daily use. Between 2015 and 2018, the use of these medicines increased, especially the new N06AX antidepressants. In addition, concomitant use of antidepressants with other DIMs was relevant, which involved benzodiazepines. Importantly, SSRIs were consumed by a considerable proportion of the population, even if risk of using these medicines may be greater into the firsts days of use (these medicines belong to the DRUID category I, i.e., minor influence on fitness to drive).

Lastly, it is considered necessary to carry out new actions to provide more accurate information to healthcare professionals, patients, and drivers. It would be appropriate to improve prescription and dispensing systems for medications including alerts related to antidepressants. It is necessary to propose actions to avoid the unsafe driving of vehicles by patients under treatment with antidepressants. These dissuasive actions could be the inclusion of antidepressants into the battery for road detection tests, adapt traffic regulations to the use of these medicines, information campaigns, etc. [40].

Supplementary Materials: The following are available online at <http://www.mdpi.com/1424-8247/13/4/61/s1>. Table S1: Antidepressants available in Castile and León (2015–2018). Table S2: Evolution of the Castile and León population and drivers' licenses (2015–2018). Table S3: List of the 40 DIMs more consumed in Castile and León into study period (Packages/year). Table S4: Evolution of antidepressants use in Castile and León (2015–2018). Table S5: Evolution of antidepressants use in Castile and León by DRUID classification (2015–2018).

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Table S1: Antidepressants available in Castile and León (2015 – 2018).

Type of antidepressant	Code ATC	Name	DRUID categorization
Non-selective monoamine reuptake inhibitors	N06AA02	Imipramine	II
	N06AA04	Clomipramine	II
	N06AA06	Trimipramine	II
	N06AA09	Amitriptyline	III
	N06AA10	Nortriptyline	II
	N06AA12	Doxepine	III
	N06AA21	Maprotiline	II
Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors	N06AB03	Fluoxetine	I
	N06AB04	Citalopram	I
	N06AB05	Paroxetine	I
	N06AB06	Sertraline	I
	N06AB08	Fluvoxamine	I
	N06AB10	Escitalopram	I
Monoamine oxidase A inhibitors	N06AG02	Moclobemide	I
Other antidepressants	N06AX03	Mianserin	III
	N06AX05	Trazodone	III
	N06AX11	Mirtazapine	III
	N06AX12	Bupropion	II
	N06AX14	Tianeptine	II
	N06AX16	Venlafaxine	II
	N06AX18	Reboxetine	I
	N06AX01	Duloxetine	II
	N06AX02	Agomelatine	II
	N06AX03	Desvenlafaxine	II
N06AX06	Vortioxetine	II	

Table S2: Evolution of the Castile and León population and drivers's licences (2015 – 2018).

Rank age	Population											
	2015			2016			2017			2018		
	Male	Female	Total									
0-4	45 405	42 504	87 909	44 382	41 386	85 768	42 905	40 144	83 049	41 604	39 121	80 725
5-9	50 925	48 078	99 003	50 665	47 821	98 486	50 035	47 344	97 379	48 594	45 657	94 251
10-14	49 439	47 220	96 659	49 847	47 730	97 577	50 316	48 259	98 575	51 124	48 407	99 531
15-19	48 620	46 904	95 524	48 862	46 935	95 797	48 939	46 706	95 645	49 610	47 885	97 495
20-24	54 724	53 382	108 106	53 230	52 333	105 563	52 182	51 246	103 428	51 428	50 777	102 205
25-29	62 787	61 247	124 034	61 109	59 382	120 491	59 522	57 531	117 053	58 298	56 506	114 804
30-34	75 089	71 664	146 753	71 742	68 841	140 583	68 575	66 051	134 626	65 942	63 241	129 183
35-39	90 372	87 031	177 403	87 267	83 676	170 943	83 600	80 400	164 000	79 663	76 944	156 607
40-44	92 686	89 879	182 565	92 967	90 094	183 061	92 799	89 681	182 480	92 434	89 499	181 933
45-49	93 082	91 643	184 725	93 035	91 392	184 427	92 076	90 588	182 664	91 744	89 952	181 696
50-54	93 252	90 618	183 870	93 251	91 395	184 646	93 500	91 893	185 393	92 913	92 426	185 339
55-59	87 280	84 212	171 492	88 988	85 894	174 882	89 831	86 956	176 787	90 852	87 988	178 840
60-64	72 448	69 337	141 785	75 073	72 029	147 102	77 520	74 875	152 395	79 640	77 583	157 223
65-69	65 430	66 777	132 207	66 403	67 268	133 671	67 615	68 053	135 668	67 660	67 825	135 485
70-74	56 526	61 968	118 494	58 076	63 396	121 472	58 913	64 067	122 980	60 320	64 908	125 228
75-79	45 154	56 939	102 093	43 540	53 807	97 347	43 510	52 990	96 500	46 205	55 251	101 456
80-84	44 543	62 354	106 897	44 319	62 772	107 091	42 312	60 175	102 487	39 465	56 065	95 530
85-89	27 547	46 335	73 882	28 618	47 555	76 173	29 407	48 337	77 744	29 731	48 690	78 421
≥ 90	13 282	30 034	43 316	14 119	31 809	45 928	14 662	32 970	47 632	15 333	34 407	49 740
Total	1 168 591	1 208 126	2 376 717	1 165 493	1 205 515	2 371 008	1 158 219	1 198 266	2 356 485	1 152 560	1 193 132	2 345 692

Rank age	Driver's licence census											
	2015			2016			2017			2018		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
15-19	9 282	5 586	14 868	9 238	5 634	14 872	8 357	4 689	13 046	8 702	5 102	13 804
20-24	43 294	35 387	78 681	42 165	34 280	76 445	40 859	33 207	74 066	39 837	32 570	72 407
25-29	55 831	50 618	106 449	53 617	48 755	102 372	51 913	46 861	98 774	50 269	45 329	95 598
30-34	69 810	61 387	131 197	66 192	58 489	124 681	62 677	56 134	118 811	59 765	53 560	113 325
35-39	86 841	75 838	162 679	83 112	72 880	155 992	79 204	70 129	149 333	74 693	66 771	141 464
40-44	89 294	76 277	165 571	88 673	76 856	165 529	88 025	76 717	164 742	87 163	76 513	163 676
45-49	90 151	74 310	164 461	89 641	74 389	164 030	88 611	74 242	162 853	87 961	74 534	162 495
50-54	90 450	67 282	157 732	90 290	69 036	159 326	90 158	70 695	160 853	89 420	72 062	161 482
55-59	85 820	56 346	142 166	87 607	59 781	147 388	88 543	62 443	150 986	89 826	64 796	154 622
60-64	71 450	36 255	107 705	74 219	40 173	114 392	76 748	44 338	121 086	79 194	48 281	127 475
65-69	62 572	23 964	86 536	63 824	26 068	89 892	65 577	28 466	94 043	65 978	30 748	96 726
70-74	51 161	12 390	63 551	52 595	13 755	66 350	53 663	15 096	68 759	55 094	16 442	71 536
75-79	35 993	5 000	40 993	34 852	5 277	40 129	35 960	6 008	41 968	38 829	7 105	45 934
80-84	28 304	1 941	30 245	28 194	2 055	30 249	27 809	2 319	30 128	26 500	2 491	28 991
85-89	14 160	429	14 589	14 133	484	14 617	14 548	588	15 136	14 814	661	15 475
≥ 90	2 944	22	2 966	5 669	50	5 719	6 176	77	6 253	7 350	112	7 462
Total	887 357	583 032	1 470 389	884 021	587 962	1 471 983	878 828	592 009	1 470 837	875 395	597 077	1 472 472

Table S3: List of the 40 DIMs more consumed in Castile and León into the study period (Packages/year).

Code ATC	Name	Packages	Code ATC	Name	Packages
N02BB02	Metamizole sodium	1 189 861	N05BA05	Potassium clorazepate	160 627
N05BA06	Lorazepam	989 565	N05AH04	Quetiapine	158 143
N05BA12	Alprazolam	861 791	N06AA09	Amitriptyline	152 437
N02AJ13	Tramadol and paracetamol	683 935	N03AX14	Levetiracetam	130 749
N05CD06	Lormetazepam	582 253	N06AX05	Trazodone	130 569
N05BA08	Bromazepam	391 733	N02AX02	Tramadol	129 998
N03AX16	Pregabalin	277 073	N05AH03	Olanzapine	100 752
N06AB10	Escitalopam	274 420	N03AE01	Clonazepam	100 692
N02AJ06	Codeine and Paracetamol	273 087	N06AB04	Citalopram	96 353
N05BA01	DIAZEPAM	269 764	N06AX23	Desvenlafaxine	92 661
N05CF02	ZOLPIDEM	254 270	N06AB03	Fluoxetine	87 875
N06AB06	Setraline	244 838	N03AG01	Valproic acid	86 492
N06AX11	Mirtazapine	240 745	N04BA02	Levodopa and decarboxylase inhibitor	86 430
N06AX16	Venlafaxine	229 529	N05AL01	Sulpiride	84 765
A10BD07	Metformin and sitagliptin	212 812	A10BH01	Sitagliptine	83 896
N06AX21	Duloxetine	189 961	N03AX12	Gabapentine	83 492
N06AB05	Paroxetine	189 552	A10BB09	Gliclazide	82 833
A10AE04	Insuline glargin	185 578	A10BX02	Repaglinide	80 218
N02AB03	Fentanyl	182 729	N05AX08	Risperidone	79 294
A10BD08	Metformin and vildagliptin	179 957	A10BH05	Linagliptine	78 734

Table S4. Evolution of antidepressants use in Castile and León (2015 – 2018)

	Population % (95CI)				Drivers % (95CI)			
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2015	2016	2017	2018
Antidepressants								
Non-selective monoamine reuptake inhibitors								
Total	1.01 (1 - 1.02)	1.09 (1.08 - 1.1)	1.12 (1.11 - 1.13)	1.23 (1.22 - 1.24)	0.68 (0.67 - 0.69)	0.79 (0.78 - 0.8)	0.83 (0.82 - 0.84)	0.92 (0.9 - 0.94)
Male	0.51 (0.5 - 0.52)	0.57 (0.56 - 0.58)	0.58 (0.57 - 0.59)	0.65 (0.64 - 0.66)	0.53 (0.51 - 0.55)	0.59 (0.57 - 0.61)	0.61 (0.59 - 0.63)	0.69 (0.67 - 0.71)
Female	1.49 (1.47 - 1.51)	1.6 (1.58 - 1.62)	1.65 (1.63 - 1.67)	1.79 (1.77 - 1.81)	0.91 (0.89 - 0.93)	1.09 (1.06 - 1.12)	1.15 (1.12 - 1.18)	1.26 (1.23 - 1.29)
	X ² =50.326; p=0.001	X ² =48.125; p=0.001	X ² =39.478; p=0.001	X ² =52.147; p=0.001	X ² =1746.258; p=0.001	X ² =1896.324; p=0.001	X ² =1986.214; p=0.001	X ² =1896.247; p=0.001
Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors								
Total	4.61 (4.58 - 4.64)	5.15 (5.12 - 5.18)	4.96 (4.93 - 4.99)	5.24 (5.21 - 5.27)	2.98 (2.95 - 3.01)	3.44 (3.41 - 3.47)	3.33 (3.3 - 3.36)	3.53 (3.5 - 3.56)
Male	2.43 (2.4 - 2.46)	2.79 (2.76 - 2.82)	2.66 (2.63 - 2.69)	2.86 (2.83 - 2.89)	2.45 (2.42 - 2.48)	2.77 (2.74 - 2.8)	2.67 (2.64 - 2.7)	2.86 (2.83 - 2.89)
Female	6.73 (6.69 - 6.77)	7.43 (7.38 - 7.48)	7.18 (7.13 - 7.23)	7.53 (7.48 - 7.58)	3.78 (3.73 - 3.83)	4.45 (4.4 - 4.5)	4.31 (4.26 - 4.36)	4.52 (4.47 - 4.57)
	X ² =985.254; p=0.001	X ² =1058.981; p=0.001	X ² =1125.698; p=0.001	X ² =974.251; p=0.001	X ² =6587.149; p=0.001	X ² =6418.187; p=0.001	X ² =6725.792; p=0.001	X ² =6658.217; p=0.001
Other antidepressants								
Total	3.14 (3.12 - 3.16)	3.81 (3.79 - 3.83)	3.73 (3.71 - 3.75)	4.17 (4.14 - 4.2)	1.96 (1.94 - 1.98)	2.43 (2.41 - 2.45)	2.4 (2.38 - 2.42)	2.66 (2.63 - 2.69)
Male	1.9 (1.88 - 1.92)	2.39 (2.36 - 2.42)	2.31 (2.28 - 2.34)	2.65 (2.62 - 2.68)	1.89 (1.86 - 1.92)	2.29 (2.26 - 2.32)	2.26 (2.23 - 2.29)	2.53 (2.5 - 2.56)
Female	4.34 (4.3 - 4.38)	5.18 (5.14 - 5.22)	5.11 (5.07 - 5.15)	5.65 (5.61 - 5.69)	2.08 (2.04 - 2.12)	2.63 (2.59 - 2.67)	2.61 (2.57 - 2.65)	2.83 (2.79 - 2.87)
	X ² =678.241; p=0.001	X ² =698.875; p=0.001	X ² =685.458; p=0.001	X ² =648.578; p=0.001	X ² =5420.369; p=0.001	X ² =5698.439; p=0.001	X ² =5324.946; p=0.001	X ² =5987.781; p=0.001

Abbreviations: 95CI. confidence interval

Table S5. Evolution of antidepressants use in Castile and León by DRUID classification (2015 – 2018)

	Population % (95CI)				Drivers % (95CI)			
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2015	2016	2017	2018
DRUID clasiffication								
1								
Total	4.63 (4.6 - 4.66)	5.17 (5.14 - 5.2)	4.98 (4.95 - 5.01)	5.26 (5.23 - 5.29)	2.99 (2.96 - 3.02)	3.46 (3.43 - 3.49)	3.34 (3.31 - 3.37)	3.54 (3.51 - 3.57)
Male	2.44 (2.41 - 2.47)	2.8 (2.77 - 2.83)	2.67 (2.64 - 2.7)	2.87 (2.84 - 2.9)	2.46 (2.43 - 2.49)	2.79 (2.76 - 2.82)	2.68 (2.65 - 2.71)	2.87 (2.84 - 2.9)
Female	6.76 (6.72 - 6.8)	7.46 (7.41 - 7.51)	7.21 (7.16 - 7.26)	7.56 (7.51 - 7.61)	3.79 (3.74 - 3.84)	4.47 (4.42 - 4.52)	4.32 (4.27 - 4.37)	4.53 (4.48 - 4.58)
	X ² =895.214; p=0.001	X ² =986.325; p=0.001	X ² =854.214; p=0.001	X ² =995.687; p=0.001	X ² =6358.214; p=0.001	X ² =5987.147; p=0.001	X ² =6398.257; p=0.001	X ² =5987.214; p=0.001
2								
Total	2.06 (2.04 - 2.08)	2.28 (2.26 - 2.3)	2.26 (2.24 - 2.28)	2.44 (2.42 - 2.46)	1.37 (1.35 - 1.39)	1.62 (1.6 - 1.64)	1.63 (1.61 - 1.65)	1.75 (1.73 - 1.77)
Male	1.15 (1.13 - 1.17)	1.3 (1.28 - 1.32)	1.3 (1.28 - 1.32)	1.41 (1.39 - 1.43)	1.23 (1.21 - 1.25)	1.38 (1.36 - 1.4)	1.4 (1.38 - 1.42)	1.5 (1.47 - 1.53)
Female	2.93 (2.9 - 2.96)	3.22 (3.19 - 3.25)	3.19 (3.16 - 3.22)	3.44 (3.41 - 3.47)	1.6 (1.57 - 1.63)	1.98 (1.94 - 2.02)	1.97 (1.93 - 2.01)	2.12 (2.08 - 2.16)
	X ² =70.289; p=0.001	X ² =65.365; p=0.001	X ² =69.587; p=0.001	X ² =67.354; p=0.001	X ² =1658.247; p=0.001	X ² =1587.965; p=0.001	X ² =1625.387; p=0.001	X ² =1710.256; p=0.001
3								
Total	2.42 (2.4 - 2.44)	3.03 (3.01 - 3.05)	3 (2.98 - 3.02)	3.41 (3.39 - 3.43)	1.48 (1.46 - 1.5)	1.87 (1.85 - 1.89)	1.87 (1.85 - 1.89)	2.11 (2.09 - 2.13)
Male	1.46 (1.44 - 1.48)	1.9 (1.88 - 1.92)	1.83 (1.81 - 1.85)	2.16 (2.13 - 2.19)	1.4 (1.38 - 1.42)	1.76 (1.73 - 1.79)	1.73 (1.7 - 1.76)	1.99 (1.96 - 2.02)
Female	3.36 (3.33 - 3.39)	4.11 (4.07 - 4.15)	4.13 (4.09 - 4.17)	4.62 (4.58 - 4.66)	1.59 (1.56 - 1.62)	2.04 (2 - 2.08)	2.08 (2.04 - 2.12)	2.29 (2.25 - 2.33)
	X ² =587.145; p=0.001	X ² =699.247; p=0.001	X ² =654.228; p=0.001	X ² =630.259; p=0.001	X ² =4458.698; p=0.001	X ² =4698.357; p=0.001	X ² =4968.587; p=0.001	X ² =4789.653; p=0.001

Abbreviations: 95CI. confidence interval